

An Ecoepidemiological assessment of Low Coverage Children Immunization Rates in Naâma, southwest Algeria: A Multidisciplinary Approach

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Abstract

Background: The World Health Organization (WHO) has stated statistics indicating poor immunization coverage in Algeria, which is indicated by local statistics, which threatens public health.

Methods: This paper presents a multidisciplinary approach to understanding and addressing the issue of low coverage rates of children immunization in Naâma province southwest of Algeria. After conducting a survey of comprehensive samples of children born in 2020 and 2021 in the province and their vaccination rates, and through the lens of ecoepidemiology, we examine the interconnected factors contributing to this problem.

Results: Through the comprehensive survey of samples of children residing in the district born in 2020 and 2021, we obtain low vaccination rates of 78.53 % for the measles vaccine in 2020 and 68.14 % in 2021. As for the other vaccinations, they do not exceed 85 % of the target group.

Discussion: According to our findings, the state of Naâma's population distribution is significantly influenced by its topography and geographical features, which has a direct impact on children's vaccination rates due to the difficulty of accessing immunization centres'. The local community's rumours and religious convictions have also contributed significantly to the drop-in childhood immunization rates in this area.

Conclusion: Ecoepidemiology can help understand low immunization rates in Naâma Province, Algeria. A multidisciplinary strategy involving social, environmental, and biological sciences can ensure high immunization rates and securing public health by preventing the transmission of diseases from south to north.

Keywords: Ecoepidemiology, Immunization coverage, Socio-economic, Healthcare accessibility, Measles-containing-vaccine, Pneumococcal conjugate vaccine, Naâma province, Algeria

Introduction

Vaccination is the process of injecting a vaccine (a biological material) into the body in order to encourage the recipient's immune system to make antibodies or cause other changes that will provide future protection against specific infectious diseases. Vaccines trigger immune system modifications that provide protection (1).

Vaccination coverage is defined as the total number of infants who have gotten all required doses of the chosen vaccine in the previous 18 months divided by the annual target population multiplied by one hundred. It is an essential metric of vaccination coverage in a population, and high routine vaccination rates can help control vaccine-preventable diseases (2). Immunization is commonly regarded as one of the most effective ways to reduce the spread of infectious diseases and improve public health (2,3).

However, in recent years, the province of Naama in Algeria has experienced alarmingly low vaccination rates, which is one of the problems that Algeria faces in some vaccinations (e.g., PCV3 and MCV2), as shown in the two tables (Tables 1 and 2), posing a significant threat to the population's well-being. This critique seeks to draw attention to this essential issue through an ecoepidemiological lens, emphasizing the significance of a multidisciplinary approach in addressing the root causes of low immunization rates and offering broad remedies. By looking at the bigger picture, we may create targeted strategies to boost vaccination rates and reduce the related public health concerns.

Vaccination has cut measles mortality from 761,000 in 2000 to 128,000 in 2021. Vaccination against measles, mumps, and rubella (in months 11 and 18 of the Expanded National Programme) is also contributing to measles control and mitigation in Algeria. To understand the significance of vaccine coverage, consider that a 74% decrease in immunization against measles, mumps, and rubella in 2020 (Table 1), followed by a 71% fall in 2022 (Table 2), resulted in the onset of epidemics and disruptions to public health, as will be discussed.

Materials and methods

Ecoepidemiology uses a multidisciplinary approach to investigate the dynamic interconnections of human populations, diseases, and the environment. This field integrates quantitative and qualitative research methodologies, such as data analysis, mathematical modeling, social network analysis, and qualitative interviews. This ecoepidemiological critique seeks to analyze the multifaceted factors contributing to low

vaccination rates in the province from a multidisciplinary perspective, including socioeconomic, cultural, and healthcare system elements, in order to provide a comprehensive understanding of the underlying factors influencing low Coverage Immunization rates. The study was based on presenting vaccination rates for children in the district and then highlighting the main reasons for the decline in rates by referring to underlying conditions, either from the literature or through direct observation by visiting several rural residential areas and maternal and child health units where vaccinations are administered.

Statistical Data

During the 2018 Ouargla and El Oued epidemics, vaccination campaigns reached 43,000 children aged 6 to 14 in Ouargla and 39,000 in El Oued province. In statements to Algeria Press Service (APS), Djamel Forar, director of prevention at the Algerian Ministry of Health, attributed the outbreak in the two southern provinces to residents' refusal to vaccinate their children during the ministry's two vaccination campaigns launched in March 2017 and January 2018.

After consulting the local health sector administration's database in Naâma Province, comprehensive survey samples were acquired for the children targeted for vaccination, with the target group determined by subtracting deaths from total births. These findings provide a preliminary estimate of the province's immunization rate among its youngsters.

Following the occurrence of epidemics and the announcement of a thorough vaccination program against diseases creating public health difficulties, this study conducted detailed surveys of all children living in Algeria's Naâma province. These surveys included all children born between January 1, 2020 and December 31, 2021, as well as their vaccine coverage rates. The primary challenges to this process will be examined from an ecoepidemiological standpoint, drawing on the literature and firsthand observation on-site.

Results

Vaccinations are one of the most efficient public health strategies, yet their uptake stagnated in the decade preceding Covid-19. The Covid-19 epidemic, its consequences, and immunization efforts pressured healthcare systems in 2020 and 2021 (Table 3), resulting in significant setbacks. Globally, however, there are signs of recovery: by 2022, the immunization rate against diphtheria, pertussis, tetanus, and Haemophilus influenzae Type B (DPT-HiB) will have nearly returned to 2019 levels (1).

Figure 1 displays MCV2 and PCV3 vaccine coverage rates from 2010 to 2023, as estimated by WHO and UNICEF, as well as the government (7,8).

Looking at the findings, it can be seen that the government's estimates for childhood immunization rates were incorrect due to a number of issues that will be explored later, in contrast to the World Health Organization's scientific and rational analyses (4, 9, 10). This is due to numerous factors:

- **Ecoepidemiology: Understanding the Complexity of Childhood Immunization Trends**

Ecoepidemiology is an interdisciplinary discipline of research that integrates concepts from ecology with an awareness of the character of the region, such as the abundance of distant locations, rugged terrain, and harsh climate (11, 12); epidemiology By understanding the region's epidemiological history (for example, the prevalence of viral hepatitis A) and public health risk factors, as well as social sciences (13, 14), researchers can investigate the factors that influence disease patterns in communities. Applying ecoepidemiology to the study of low childhood immunization rates in Naâma Province, Algeria, allows us to investigate the complex interplay of biological, environmental, and social factors influencing immunization habits.

- **Biological Factors**

Biological variables influence people's decisions about immunization. Understanding vaccine immunology features and safety profiles is critical for overcoming vaccination reluctance. Furthermore, understanding the frequency and transmission dynamics of infectious illnesses is critical for emphasizing the long-term benefits of mass vaccination in averting outbreaks and safeguarding vulnerable populations. Policies such as mandatory school vaccination laws and regulations that require evidence of certain vaccines or serological testing of previous illnesses aim to increase and maintain herd immunity against diseases that can spread quickly (e.g., measles, mumps, etc.) among the majority of the people around them (15).

Given the area's rural setting, the local community uses medicinal plants for traditional treatments (for both adults and children) without seeking medical advice for a diagnosis or being aware of the primary causes of illnesses or the negative consequences of traditional medicinal plant use. Vaccination is also viewed skeptically in the rural community, with preference given to spontaneously acquired immunity (16, 17).

- **Environmental Factors**

- **Geographic and Ecological Barriers (18):** Figures 2, 3, and 4 show the topographical geography of Naâma province, including remote and isolated locations such as El Kesdir and Sfisifa, where nomads live in difficult mountainous terrain.

The vast number of nomadic areas in the north of the wilaya (the towns of Ben Ammar and El Kesdir), the severe environment, the large number of nomads, and the lack of health facilities are among the most significant barriers to the success of vaccine coverage programs. The southern regions, rural populations, and nomadic Bedouins face tough mountainous terrain in addition to a semi-desert environment.

All of these factors may combine to limit access to healthcare institutions and make it harder to reach communities. These constraints can have a major impact on immunization rates (19,20).

Figure 4 shows that the location of six high-population municipalities in the province's south is attributable to ecological and topographical causes.

The passage of the Atlas desert mountain range (Figure 5) over the province's south resulted in climate change, as evidenced by the presence of climate Arid lower Average fresh and Arid lower very high fresh (Figures 2 and 3), prompting the population to relocate to the province's south and away from climate arid superior fresh, which presents difficulties in living. These terrain environmental factors influenced population distribution, which in turn influenced health coverage distribution, as they were concentrated only in urban areas, primarily in the province's south, with nomads scattered throughout the province's north and northwest (21).

Table 1. Immunization coverage of PCV3 and MCV2 in Algeria (2020).(4, 5, 6)

Indicator	Fact Value Numeric	First Period
Measles-containing-vaccine second-dose (MCV2) immunization coverage by the nationally recommended age (%)	74.00	2020
Pneumococcal conjugate vaccines (PCV3) immunization coverage among 1-year-olds (%)	83.00	2020
Hib (Hib3) immunization coverage among 1-year-olds (%)	84.00	2020

Table 2. Immunization coverage of PCV3 and MCV2 in Algeria (2022) (4, 5, 6)

Indicator	Fact Value Numeric	First Period
Measles-containing-vaccine second-dose (MCV2) immunization coverage by the nationally recommended age (%)	71.00	2022
Pneumococcal conjugate vaccines (PCV3) immunization coverage among 1-year-olds (%)	74.00	2022
Hib (Hib3) immunization coverage among 1-year-olds (%)	77.00	2022

Figure 1. Immunization coverage rates of MCV2 and PCV3 from 2010 to 2023 with WHO and UNICEF estimates, Government estimates

Table 3. The target group of children for vaccination and the rates of vaccination for: Measles, Mumps, And Rubella (MMR) I Vaccine; Pentavalent (Diphtheria, Pertussis (whooping cough), Tetanus, Haemophilus influenzae Type B, Pneumococcal conjugate Vaccine) III Vaccine in Naâma Province, Algeria. (Information obtained from the provincial health department)

A comprehensive survey sample of children targeted for vaccination for the year 2020

Months	Births	Deaths	Target population	Measles, Mumps, And Rubella (MMR) I Vaccine	Percentage	Pentavalent III Vaccine	Percentage	Measles, Mumps, And Rubella (MMR) II Vaccine	Percentage
January	550	17	533	482	90.43	476	89.31	461	86.49
February	437	10	427	377	88.29	385	90.16	363	85.01
March	487	4	483	425	87.99	380	78.67	394	81.57
April	530	12	545	476	87.34	455	83.49	448	82.20
May	572	8	564	492	87.23	481	85.28	432	76.60
June	666	14	652	545	83.59	517	79.29	439	67.33
July	641	14	627	535	85.33	497	79.27	516	82.30
August	515	14	501	447	89.22	442	88.22	379	75.65
September	466	6	460	417	90.65	421	91.52	410	89.13
October	583	15	568	466	82.04	485	85.39	426	75.00
November	429	3	426	367	86.15	361	84.74	330	77.46
December	489	7	482	429	89.00	373	77.39	324	67.22
TOTAL	6365	124	6268	5458	87.08	5273	84.13	4922	78.53

A comprehensive survey sample of children targeted for vaccination for the year 2021

January	491	8	483	407	84.27	376	77.85	361	74.74
February	399	7	392	352	89.80	348	88.78	312	79.59
March	442	10	432	359	83.10	366	84.72	288	66.67
April	391	3	388	349	89.95	323	83.25	276	71.13
May	468	5	463	372	80.35	368	79.48	316	68.25
June	530	13	517	433	83.75	434	83.95	414	80.08
July	578	8	570	461	80.88	450	78.95	427	74.91
August	612	8	604	508	105.30	494	81.79	514	85.10
September	532	4	528	501	94.89	486	92.05	460	87.12
October	531	10	521	436	83.69	425	81.57	229	43.95
November	469	5	464	403	86.85	395	85.13	183	39.44
December	467	6	461	381	82.65	387	83.95	173	37.53
TOTAL	5900	99	5801	4962	82.53	4852	83.64	3953	68.14

Figure 2. Population map of the Naâma region (21)

Figure 3. Bioclimatic maps of the Naâma region (21)

Figure 4. Municipalities of Naâma province.

Figure 5. Topography map of the Naâma region

Figure 6. Naama province Map showing the position of the Maternal and Child Protection Units

Figure 7. Topography map of the Naama region (Gaaloul village coordinates is: 32.937742°, -1.123602 °)

- **Socioeconomic Factors**
 - ✓ **Income Disparity:** NAAMA province has a high level of income disparity, with most nomad households unable to afford to travel to acquire vital healthcare treatments, such as vaccinations. Due to a lack of financial resources and a subsistence lifestyle, these families use healthcare facilities less frequently and have lower immunization rates (22, 23).
Education Level: Low education levels in certain groups might contribute to a lack of awareness and understanding of the need and advantages of immunization, resulting in lower vaccination rates. Despite the government's efforts, many nomads in this region lack access to education, and children are not enrolled in school. School enrollment alerts the detection and follow-up unit in school medicine to the delay in vaccination among kids and the need to catch up, thus nomadic children suffer from not enrolling in school, which prevents them from receiving health-care (22).
- **Cultural Factors**
 - ✓ **Misinformation and Vaccine Hesitancy:** Cultural views and misconceptions regarding immunization can cause parental hesitation to vaccines. Rumors, myths, and disinformation about vaccine safety and efficacy can spread throughout communities, resulting in a decrease in vaccination coverage (23-25). One of the most prominent examples is what happened recently with polio vaccination, where rumors circulated about only vaccinating children in the southern states, and this question was raised by even health professionals, demonstrating the lack of information and the spread of misinformation (26).
 - ✓ **Religious and Cultural Practices:** Certain religious or cultural beliefs may discourage or prevent communities from immunizing their children. Many people of these communities have a low level of knowledge, which contributes to the development of misconceptions and cultural intolerance, as well as the perception that such immunizations are a fraud, clinical trials, or the source of health problems in their children. Understanding and addressing these attitudes while maintaining cultural sensitivity is critical to boosting vaccination rates (27).
- **Healthcare System Factors**
 - ✓ **Accessibility and Availability:** Limited access to healthcare services, including vaccination facilities, can reduce vaccination coverage. Long distances to nearby health centers, as well as limited operation hours, may make it difficult for families seeking immunizations for children. Figure 6 depicts the unequal distribution of maternal and child protection units across the province's regions, with the northern and northwestern parts (which correspond to ecological and geographical reasons in terms of population distribution) suffering from poor health coverage, which is one of the most significant reasons for the decline in immunization coverage among children in those areas.
 - ✓ **Distance:** One of the barriers to health coverage in Naama province is the province's vast size. For example, in figure 7, the distance between the village of Gaaloul and the nearest maternal and child care unit (Ain Ben Khelil municipality) is 53.19 km, regardless of how far away the population lives.

- ✓ **Health Service Infrastructure:** Inadequate healthcare infrastructure, which includes insufficient staffing, cold chain storage, and vaccine stockouts, can have a detrimental impact on vaccination rates. Improving the healthcare system's ability to provide vaccinations is critical. Logistical support at Naama province health facilities is low and cannot meet the state's population's public health needs (e.g., vaccine coverage), particularly in rural villages and nomad communities.
- ✓ **Healthcare Provider Knowledge and Communication:** Low immunization rates can be attributed to healthcare practitioners' lack of awareness about recommended immunization schedules and poor communication. Training healthcare providers and improving effective communication tactics can help to solve this issue. Health workers in the respective health facilities must provide adequate information about childhood vaccinations (including start, return, and completion) for each antenatal care, postpartum mothers, and mothers attending the vaccination site at each visit, as well as communicate the specific vaccination schedule to mothers via another mechanism, such as a phone call (28).

Discussion

Considering the previous research, it can be seen that the low immunization coverage in the region is due to several factors, the most important of which are i) the nature of the rural area and the nomadic population, which impose special procedures that differ from those applied at the level of urban areas and cities; ii) The economic aspect: infrastructure (ease of access to healthcare facilities) and standard of living deprive individuals of the ability to achieve the required level of health through examinations and healthcare; iii)

The community's culture and scientific level are critical to the acceptance of proper health culture and disease spread.

These findings are based on a specific scientific technique that relies on a multidisciplinary examination of vaccine coverage rates over a certain time span in Algeria's Naama region, which has its own unique geographical and sociological characteristics. As a result of the differences between regions, comparing studies from this perspective is difficult. As a result, remedies were presented to address the issue on a more limited scale. Future research that examine broader time spans will yield more effective findings.

Multidisciplinary Approach: Towards Comprehensive Solutions

Addressing low child immunization rates in Naâma Province necessitates a comprehensive, multidisciplinary approach that draws on expertise from numerous fields. Collaboration among scientists, medical experts, public health officials, policymakers, and community stakeholders is critical for designing effective interventions to address the underlying reasons of low vaccination rates.

- **Strengthening healthcare infrastructure:** Improving access to immunization clinics, particularly in impoverished regions, is critical for increasing vaccination rates. Expanding vaccination coverage in schools and deploying mobile immunization units can improve accessibility.
- **Education and awareness campaigns:** Utilizing evidence-based communication strategies to address vaccine hesitancy and counter misinformation are pivotal. Collaborating with social scientists, health communication experts, and community leaders can ensure the development of culturally sensitive educational campaigns that resonate with different populations.
- **Interventions and Policy Recommendations:** Improving vaccine policy and regulation can significantly boost vaccination rates (29).
- **Community Engagement:** Collaboration with local communities and overcoming vaccination reluctance are critical. Working with community leaders, healthcare providers, and educators can assist build personalized educational programs to dispel myths and boost vaccine acceptance.
- **Enhancing Surveillance and Response Systems:** Improving disease surveillance systems and encouraging proactive reporting

can help with early detection and response to outbreaks. This involves real-time monitoring of vaccination coverage, tracking of vaccine waste, and the implementation of vaccination reminder systems.

- **Research and surveillance:** Active surveillance systems and continuous research are critical for tracking vaccine coverage rates, identifying areas of poor immunization, and understanding the variables that contribute to vaccine reluctance. This data can be used to inform targeted treatments and assess the efficacy of initiatives that have been adopted.

Conclusion

Ecoepidemiology provides a useful framework for understanding the multidimensional nature of low childhood immunization rates in Naâma Province, Algeria. Comprehensive strategies for addressing the underlying reasons of this troubling trend might be established by taking a multidisciplinary approach that incorporates biological, environmental, and social studies. We can work together with scientists, healthcare providers, politicians, and the community to ensure high immunization rates and protect the health and well-being of children in Naâma Province, Algeria.

The region's terrain, difficult topography, and low standard of life all had a substantial impact on population dispersal, nomadism, and access to immunization facilities. It prompted the government to increase vaccination rates in order to prevent infectious disease outbreaks and the spread of infections from Africa's coast to North Africa.

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